

Fundamental knowledge of how our body gets energy

Some food we eat gets broken down into a type of sugar called “Glucose.” The glucose is what provided the body with energy. Glucose gives the body energy to work, think, and play.

Glucose is taken from our intestines to all parts of the body through the bloodstream. Glucose is used for energy inside our body cells.

Our body composes of a vast number of cells which are in very small sizes than our eyes can see.

The bloodstream is an excellent transport system. If you prick your finger or your toe... What happens? It bleeds. So that means there is blood traveling all through every little part of your body. That is transporting glucose into your cells so that your body has energy.

We need insulin, so our bodies can use glucose. Insulin is made in the pancreas.

A person with diabetes has too little insulin, or the insulin does not work properly.

Storyboard 1: Mouth moves as to chewing the apple. Animate pieces of the chewed apple moving down the food tube.

Storyboard 2: Zoom in at the stomach. Animate the stomach to move as it is digesting the food. Chunks of apples are broken down into tiny pieces. Then the word, "Glucose" appear at last.

Storyboard 3: Let lightbulb appear at last.

Storyboard 4: Let there be some movements in the blood vessels as if there is something moving.

Storyboard 5: As if zooming into the body, the cells appear at last.

The blood stream is an excellent transport system.

Storyboard 6: Similar to storyboard 4.

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Storyboard 7: At first, let the audience see the organs in the torso. After that, decrease the transparency of the very organs except for the pancreas, which positions itself at the back of the stomach. Let the transparency of the pancreas remain 100 %, and also highlight it by glowing.

Storyboard 8: Let the word “Pancreas” appear first. Then the arrow appears as to the pancreas produces “insulin”.